

DERLEME

REVIEW

DRONE USE IN EMERGENCY MEDICINE

Hatice Şeyma Akça, MD¹

¹ *University of Karamanoğlu Mehmet Bey, Department of Emergency Medicine, Karaman, Türkiye*

ABSTRACT

Drone applications can be operational, strategic or tactical. It can remove people from risky areas in terms of crisis management in natural disasters and earthquakes, and also reach those waiting to be rescued.

Delivery drones carrying relief supplies; monitoring drones monitoring areas to reach injured or victims; map drones that allow us to hold the location of the region. Essentially, the coordination that starts with map drones continues with data collection and data transmission.

In addition to effective and rapid treatment in disasters, the use of drones for medical purposes is advantageous in terms of preventing the development of complications in injured people, but regulations are needed.

Keywords: *medical drones, rapid treatment*

Correspondence to: *Hatice Şeyma Akça*

University of Karamanoğlu Mehmet Bey, Department of Emergency Medicine, Karaman, Türkiye

E-mail: haticeseymaakca@gmail.com

Orcid: 0000-0003-2823-9577

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Drones

Drones, which have entered our lives recently, have many uses. It is sometimes used in cargo delivery, sometimes in agriculture, and sometimes to ensure coordination in traffic. Drones can perform many tasks in difficult terrain. Since their energy is limited, they must be optimized and used.

Meteorological conditions, tall buildings affect the operation and battery consumption of drones. Obstacles can cause communication interruption and packet loss. Energy is undoubtedly needed not only for flying, but also for drones to perform their mission. Drones have tasks such as transporting injured victims who are located along with communication (1-4).

Work was carried out on 'Multi-drone organization' to prevent mishaps that may occur with a single drone and to organize the network connection (5). There are different methods and different algorithms. Greedy Geographic Forwarding (GGF) and Greedy Perimeter Stateless Routing (GPSR) determine location. There are methods such as the Store-Carry-Forward (SCF) method. The SPIDER algorithm is presented as a field built on recent advances in geographic routing. The SPIDER algorithm is suitable for high-density drones. In the Heuristic Greedy Packet Forwarding (HGPF) Algorithm, drone position is used. Integrated RL-based Packet Forwarding (IRLPF) Algorithm: According to a study, it consumes less energy than HGPF and has a more optimum distribution compared to DRM (Disaster response management) (6).

For drones, the term Remotely Piloted plane structures (RPAS) is used in Europe. The term UAV (Unmanned Aerial vehicle) is also used. The unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) was invented for the first time in 1849 and was developed to take its current form. Medical drones began to be used in America for the first time in 2016 with the permission of the FAA (Federal Aviation Administration) (7,8). Drone instrumentalized ambulance (ODIA) is the integration of three components such as live-stream first-aid box, webcam, and global positioning system (GPS) unit (9).

Drone applications can be operational, strategic or tactical. It can remove people from risky areas in terms of crisis management in natural disasters and earthquakes, and also reach those waiting to be rescued (10). In explosions or accidents that release dangerous gases or liquids, the drone determines the direction of spread of these toxic substances. Drones can be optimized for rapid mapping, damaged building detection and human rescue during earthquakes.

Drones can be optimized for the control of dams and the flow direction of possible floods in floods, but since it covers a large area, operational or tactical drones should be preferred for flood monitoring and control. Management of forest fires is quite difficult, visibility may be limited. However, drones are preferred because they are low cost compared to manned aircraft (11).

We know that climate conditions have changed in recent years. Drones can be used for guidance in natural disasters and can also be integrated into emergency and disaster response protocols. In this way, medical aid supplies can be delivered to many people and effective intervention can be provided. As we know, the disaster relief life cycle is divided into 4: prevention, preparation, response, recovery. In the search and rescue study conducted with drones, it was determined that the

search area of the drones was statistically significantly larger than the search team. In this study, the drone height was 60 meters (12).

According to information in 2016, there is no economic project on how to place the drone in the disaster area. Different drone methods have also been developed regarding time, route and geographical location of the disaster area. Similarly, medical aid was delivered to floods and earthquakes in Nepal and Haiti (13-15).

In addition to allowing drones to detect images in the disaster area and guide rescuers, a heat detection sensor was also developed to reach people. Thus, progress has been made in telemedicine and public health. Using drones is less costly but can sometimes cause failure at low altitude. There are also fewer permit requirements for helicopters and aircraft. In addition to transportation to disaster areas, innovations have emerged regarding the use of drones in emergency treatments. Transport of food, medical aid equipment, and medicines such as insulin was ensured.

The use of drones in no-fly zones has not yet been investigated. International agreements are needed. As of this year, we do not have any systematic and sufficient evidence regarding the use of drones in disasters. There has been an increase in publications about the use of drones in the last 10 years. Undoubtedly, advances in the field of engineering and the need to reach people waiting to be rescued faster are the reasons for this interest (16,17).

Using Drones in Emergency Medicine

While responding to emergency calls is 9 minutes in urban areas in America; This time can increase to 15 minutes in rural areas (18). In a simulation study conducted with parachute drones, a 92% successful landing rate was recorded for medical drones. (The first study) (19). Drone speed 20-100 mph. Range: 1000 miles (20). For organ transplantation, 14 drones flew at a distance of 1.5-3 miles, and the pathologist noted that there was no damage to the organs after the flight (21).

Studies were conducted in Switzerland and Canada comparing the arrival times of drones with the arrival times of ambulances, and it was concluded that drones reach patients in a shorter time than ambulances (22,23). It has also been proven to be safe in transporting blood products. It has been found that blood transfusion saves time even in cities (24).

It has been determined in studies that the transportation of epinephrine, antiepileptics, naloxone, insulin, salbutamol and lasix is also feasible by drone (25-27). Approximately 4 times more survival was detected in out-of-hospital cardiac arrest cases with shorter defibrillation time (28). In a study on drone networks, it was found that the chance of survival and neurological recovery in patients needing defibrillation increased with the use of drones for medical assistance and the cost was lower than expected, but trained and untrained rescuers were not evaluated separately. In this study, thanks to a network of 500 drones, the time for defibrillation to reach the patient was shortened approximately 3 times. Survival rate doubled (29). In a study conducted in Stockholm, it was determined that the use of drones for early defibrillation in more than 3000 out-of-hospital cardiac arrest cases arrived at the scene in a shorter time than an ambulance (30). Similar results were obtained in a study conducted in Canada (22). Drones were also used to deliver Covid vaccines, examine compliance with quarantine rules, and examine vital signs (31).

Drones for medical assistance:

Delivery drones carrying relief supplies; monitoring drones monitoring areas to reach injured or victims; map drones that allow us to hold the location of the region. Essentially, the coordination that starts with map drones continues with data collection and data transmission. In case of loss of a drone, spare drones are used to locate the lost drone (5).

Challenges of using drones in Emergency Medicine

- flight permit
- Flight time
- Emergency landing procedures
- Cost
- Care
- Security
- Internet restriction
- Limited availability of blood products
- Inability to travel long distances

Another uncertainty we have about medical drones is how to obtain patient permission. Unfortunately, this issue is still controversial. While some studies suggest that public perception is that drones will be misused; Some studies have shown that cardiac arrest is more easily intervened in the presence of a drone with an automatic external defibrillator (32). In drone-related studies, meteorological parameters such as humidity and temperature and factors such as limited field of view are generally absent. Therefore, additional studies are needed (33).

Erythrocyte suspension and fresh frozen plasma were sent from one place to another for 26.5 minutes with the help of a drone, and it was observed that there was no change in PH and blood hemogram parameters. Drones containing medical kits and medicines have also been developed. Extensive drone research has been done to develop blood transfusion tools (34-37).

In addition to effective and rapid treatment in disasters, the use of drones for medical purposes is advantageous in terms of preventing the development of complications in injured people, but regulations are needed. Medical drones used in Switzerland can travel a maximum distance of 20km and carry a load of up to 2kg (38-39).

Some sources mention the existence of medical drones that can carry payloads of up to 4 kg. When designing a drone system, take-off altitude, landing altitude, acceleration and weather conditions are taken into account. 50 meters more than the coverage area radius is the safe flight altitude. Ambulances have many more functions than drones. We cannot say that drones are always superior to ambulances in terms of cost and time, except in life-threatening situations where early intervention is required (40). Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) typically defines the type of

pneumonia acquired by patients in their homes or within the community. This condition arises as a result of an infection in the respiratory tract, often caused by various pathogens such as bacteria, viruses, or fungi (1-4). Community-acquired pneumonia is generally associated with the following symptoms, fever (an increase in body temperature), cough (particularly with or without sputum), shortness of breath (a sensation of difficulty breathing during respiration), chest pain (discomfort or pain in the chest region).

CAP is often treatable in healthy individuals. However, it can be more severe, especially in the elderly, those with weakened immune systems, or individuals with underlying health problems (1-4). Treatment typically involves antibiotics, antiviral drugs, or antifungal medications, depending on the specific type of pathogen causing the infection. Early diagnosis and appropriate treatment can often help prevent complications (5-7).

Scoring systems used for hospitalization of CAP patients are employed to assess the severity of the patient and determine appropriate treatment strategies (8-11). Here are some commonly used scoring systems for CAP patients:

Pneumonia Severity Index (PSI): PSI is a scoring system that assesses the severity of CAP. It includes various clinical and demographic factors such as the patient's age, comorbidities, vital signs, and laboratory findings.

CURB-65 Score: This scoring system uses the criteria of Confusion, Urea (>20 mg/dL), Respiratory Rate (≥ 30 breaths per minute), Blood Pressure ($<90/60$ mmHg), and age (≥ 65). Each criterion presence receives a score, and the total score determines the severity.

CRB-65 Score: Similar to CURB-65, this system includes altered Mental Status instead of Urea and assesses Confusion, Respiratory Rate, Blood Pressure, and age.

SMART-COP Score: This scoring system is based on criteria such as Systolic Blood Pressure (<90 mmHg), Multilobar Infiltrates, Altered Mental Status, Respiratory Rate (≥ 30), Tachycardia, and CO₂ (Partial pressure of carbon dioxide <30 mmHg).

These scoring systems are commonly used in clinical practice to assess the patient's condition and determine severity. However, each patient should be individually evaluated, and the treatment plan should be customized based on their clinical condition (12,13). Similarly, laboratory parameters can be used in clinical decision making.

C-reactive protein (CRP) is a type of protein produced by the liver, and its levels increase in the body in response to inflammation or infection. CRP is considered an inflammatory marker, reflecting inflammatory processes occurring in the body (14-16). In the context of CAP, CRP levels can aid in assessing the severity of the disease and monitoring the response to treatment. CRP is regarded as an indicator of inflammation and is associated with conditions such as infections, inflammatory diseases, or tissue damage (1,17,18). The relationship between mortality and CRP levels is complex, as various factors can influence this relationship. However, in general, elevated CRP levels are often associated with more severe and advanced inflammatory conditions. This is important in evaluating the overall health status of the patient and their response to treatment.

Lactate is the ionized form of lactic acid, a salt of lactic acid produced in the body. Lactic acid is an acid formed during the process of anaerobic glycolysis, which is an energy production process from glucose without the use of oxygen. During this process, glucose is converted into lactic acid, resulting in the formation of lactate (19). Lactate levels in the bloodstream are generally low, but specific conditions or diseases, especially situations where tissue oxygenation is decreased, can lead to an increase in lactate levels. Elevated lactate levels can indicate inadequate tissue perfusion and metabolic disturbances (20,21).

In CAP patients, the relationship between lactate levels and mortality is often associated with the patient's clinical condition and overall health. Elevated lactate levels may suggest that the patient has developed severe complications, such as severe infection or septic shock. Various studies have shown that high lactate levels are associated with poor prognosis and high mortality, especially in severe infections and sepsis conditions (22). However, this relationship is not specific to CAP patients and is generally associated with infections (1,23). In CAP patients, an increase in lactate levels may suggest that the patient has developed severe complications. In this case, lactate levels can play a significant role in the clinical assessment of the patient and determining the treatment plan (24,25). However, specific and comprehensive studies are needed to establish a lactate level-mortality relationship specifically for CAP.

Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) is a hematological parameter that expresses the ratio between the number of neutrophils and lymphocytes measured during a blood test. This ratio provides information about inflammatory conditions and the immune system's response. NLR is often used as an indicator of an inflammatory or immune response (26,27). Neutrophils and lymphocytes are essential components of the immune system, both being types of white blood cells (leukocytes). Neutrophils are typically associated with acute infections, while lymphocytes are generally associated with chronic infections and immune system responses (28,29). The relationship between the NLR and mortality in CAP patients has been examined in various studies (5,30,31). However, this relationship cannot be accepted as an exact and general rule due to the complexity of this interaction, and several factors can influence it.

Some studies have suggested that a high NLR may be associated with poor prognosis in CAP patients. However, due to the complexity of such relationships, it is not recommended to use NLR alone as a mortality prediction tool. It should be evaluated along with other clinical and laboratory parameters for a more accurate assessment (30,31). The patient's overall condition, comorbidities, age, gender, and other factors should also be taken into account.

As a conclusion the combined use of biomarkers and scoring systems can contribute to a more effective and personalized approach in the treatment of CAP. However, each patient is unique, and treatment plans should be tailored to individual characteristics and clinical conditions. Future research should focus on optimizing the use of these indicators and gaining a better understanding of their role in the management of CAP.

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